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Formation of the Professional Position of the Additional Education Teacher

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Abstract

The article reveals the problem of the formation of the professional position of the additional education teacher. At the present stage of sustainable, rapid development of Russian society and in the context of modernization of the national education system, the introduction of new educational standards and the professional standard "Additional education teacher of children and adults" the role of the teacher as an active subject of the educational process and a specialist, who is aspiring and capable of professional self-development, self-improvement in the process of performing a certain kind of professional activity is updated and significantly increases. These aspects acquired a particular significance in the context of the relevance of the staffing issue in additional education institutions. The purpose of the article is to justify the importance of the problem of formation of the professional position of additional education teacher, to determine the readiness of teachers for professional activities, to develop and approbate the corporate training program "The successful teacher". The leading method in the research of the indicated problem is questioning method which was used among 118 teachers and allowed to reveal the level of the readiness of additional education teachers for professional activity. The article substantiates the need to organize work on corporate training and raising the level of professional skill through the system of continuous professional development of teachers of an institution of additional education of children. The materials presented in the article confirm that new requirements for the quality of educational services against the background of the shortage of qualified specialists, exclusivity and specificity of activities in additional education accent the paramount importance of the formation of the professional position of the teacher.

Keywords: education, teacher, continuous education, additional education, postgraduate training, professional adaptation.

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Introduction

In Russia additional education of children is recognized as the most important component of the unified educational space and is the object of close attention from the public and the state.

According to the Concept of the development of additional education of children approved by the Order of the Government of the Russian Federation from September 4, 2014 № 1726-p "... nowadays, in the context of informational socialization additional education of children can become an instrument for the formation of values, worldview, civic identity of the younger generation, adaptability to the rates of social and technological changes". These guidelines require a high level of training of additional education teachers, support of their certification with the acceptance of the postulates of the professional standard and a career development model.

In modern conditions the implementation of the tasks of the Russian state in the field of educational policy requires an additional education teacher to improve teaching skills through personal and professional growth. Fundamentally new requirements to the quality of educational services against the background of the shortage of qualified specialists, exclusivity and specificity of activities in additional education accent the paramount importance of the formation of the professional position of the teacher.

At present, the institution of additional education of children in order to create favorable conditions for high quality education and versatile development of the younger generation requires the improvement of the teachers professionalism, the involvement of young specialists, the constant improvement of teaching skills, the expansion of social activity, the manifestation of an active life position, the involvement in a variety of professional contests, the dissemination of pedagogical experience. It is cardinal and rapid changes in the system of additional education dictated by the ideas of modernization and implementation of innovative technologies create an atmosphere of the need for constant professional self-improvement, confirmation of knowledge and competence of the teacher.

The problem of professional development of personality is studied today by domestic and foreign scientists in the aspect of personal and social formation of a specialist as a subject of public relations and it is one of the most relevant in psychological and pedagogical science. As noted by Garanina & Maltseva (2016) the efficiency of professional activity as well as the success of the profession mastering are subordinated to the totality of human properties that characterize the internal personal and professional potential and allow continuous self-improvement and professional self-realization. According to Zhigimont (2014) conscious self-regulation should be considered as a systemically organized process of internal mental activity of a teacher.

According to Mitina (2015) the professional development of a person should be understood "as growth, formation, integration and realization of professionally significant qualities and abilities, knowledge and skills in the activity, but the main thing is an active qualitative transformation of a person's inner world, leading to the fundamentally new structure and way of life".

From the point of view of Bicheva, Medvedeva, Povarov (2016) the advanced training of additional education teachers should be understood as an increment of personal education, deepening of the professional and cultural specialization and increasing the level of the professional competence in order to strengthen the socio-cultural component of professional activity.

The efficiency of mastering of the professional standard and preparing additional education teachers for activity depends on the organization of work on additional professional education (Lopatina, Naumova, & Malykhina, 2018; Malykhina, Kovalchuk, Maron, & Rebrova, 2018). Therefore, the task of creating a flexible system of advanced training of additional education teachers arises.

In general, the professional position of the additional education teacher is characterized by the presence of a specific set of professional knowledge, professional skills, professional motivation and embodies the unity of consciousness and activity. According to the advanced researches of the last years, the level of formation of the general and professional competences affects the success and the effectiveness of the teacher's work in the field of socialization, education and upbringing of younger generation in the conditions of the new society that recognizes innovation and high technology as priorities. In the complex system of global world education, the idea of focusing on the concept of lifelong learning and life wide

learning is sharply marked. That is why the focus is shifted to the need to create a system of continuous professional education, retraining and advanced training of additional education teachers.

Due to the specific nature of the activity, the institutions of additional education of children are forced "to grow up" specialists within their structure, denoting as a priority the administration's policy as a self-learning organization in the frames of the management of the quality of the educational process. On this basis we designated a very acute problem: how to ensure continuous professional education and effective training based on the development of the professional competence of additional education teachers within the institution.

Research methods

Research methods

In the course of the research the following methods were used: theoretical (analysis, synthesis, generalization), diagnostic (questioning, testing), empirical (study of regulatory documentation, scientific and methodical and educational literature, expert estimates and the results of pilot studies, pedagogical observation), experimental (stating, forming, control experiments), mathematical statistics at the assessment of the results.

Experimental research base

Experimental base of the research is Municipal autonomous children's education institution "Palace of Pioneers and Schoolchildren of Orsk" (Orenburg Region).

Stages of research

The research of the problem was carried out in three stages. At the first stage the theoretical analysis of the existing methodological approaches in philosophical, psychological and pedagogical scientific literature, dissertation works, theories and techniques of pedagogical researches was carried out; the problem, the purpose, methods and investigation stages were defined. The leading method of the research is questioning method which was used among 118 teachers and allowed to reveal the level of readiness of additional education teachers for professional activity.

At the second stage the program of the corporate training "The successful teacher" was developed and approved. At the third stage the analysis of the results of the program implementation was done.

Results

The basis of the experimental work is the substantiation of the importance of the problem of the formation of the professional position of the additional education teacher of children, the definition of teachers' readiness for professional activity, the development and approbation of the corporate training program "The successful teacher" in the additional education institution in Orsk.

The results of the interview and the analysis of the reporting documentation of the institution for the purpose of monitoring the changes and the movements of the personnel structure of the Palace of pioneers showed that the institution had a developed stable professional team, numbering 118 people, including: administrative and managerial staff - 9 people, teaching staff - 109 people. It is necessary to note that in the last two years, there is a stability of the indicators of the total number of the teaching staff of the institution.

The carried-out analysis showed the stability of the following indicators: the prevalence of the employees in the age category of 35-55 years (86% of collective number), that demonstrates the presence of the stable efficient team and at the same time the aging of the personnel structure; close quantitative indices on the age categories confirm the systematic generational change in the collective.

The emotional assessment (questionnaire survey) of the prospects for their professional future among teachers looks like this: 82% of respondents clearly see their professional future; 6% have some doubts that they correctly chose their profession; 12% think with fear that they will fail in the professional activity. The revealed doubt is due to the uncertainty of young teachers in their abilities and professional capabilities, the contradiction between the readiness for work in the system of additional education, expectations and a real situation.

The results of the methodology for determining the readiness of teachers for professional activities indicate the optimal level at 86% of respondents, the acceptable level at 12%, the critical level at 2%; no invalid level detected.

The received results formed the basis for the development of the program of the corporate training for teachers "The successful teacher". The program was built taking into account the organizational culture that developed in the institution (a collective vision of the problem, a possibility for training, supporting culture, the trusting management, motivation). The main idea of the program is the recognition of the need to realize own success at any stage of pedagogical activity by a teacher. The goal of the program is to improve the level of professional skill of a teacher through a system of continuous professional development.

The program has a modular design: the "Awakening" module (for young professionals and newly arrived teachers for the purpose of professional adaptation and "hold" in the profession), the "Ascent" module (for steadily working teachers who have qualification category I or passed certification for compliance with the position held); the "Recognition" module (teachers during the attestation, preparation and participation in professional skill contests), the "Accomplishment" module (teachers with the highest qualification category, mentors, experts), the "Stalker" module (administrative-and-management staff).

The "Awakening" module program is focused on the target audience in the person of young specialists and newly arrived teachers with work experience in the institution of additional education of children no more than two years. The basis for the reference of a teacher to this target audience may be a long break in teaching activity, requiring updating of basic knowledge and correcting of approaches to teaching. The content of training within the framework of this module includes advanced training courses, participation in webinars, problem regional seminars, methodical integration of structural units of the institution, visiting other teachers' open classes, as well as the introduction of mentoring technologies in the framework of administrative, methodological and psychological-pedagogical support.

The "Ascent" module program is basic in the structure of the corporate training program and has the largest target audience, they are steadily working teachers who have the first, less often the highest qualification category, and also passed certification for the compliance with the position held. Training teachers in the content of the specified module involves the formation of personal qualities and professional competences of additional education teachers in the field of setting goals and objectives of pedagogical activity, professional motivation, information literacy. The main forms of the training are work in creative groups of teachers, research of a methodological subject, coaching, work with materials of the information and methodological center, work on the subject of professional self-education.

The "Recognition" module in its content is aimed at additional education teachers in the period of certification, preparation and participation in professional skill contests. Training and methodological support of teachers assumes acquaintance with the acts regulating the certification procedure, work at the compilation and dissemination of pedagogical experience, publishing activities, publication of scientific articles, correction of practical activities, participation in methodical actions. The transfer of a teacher to the next target audience is determined individually on the basis of the successful completion of the certification procedure.

The "Accomplishment" module is intended for teachers with the highest qualification category, acting as mentors and experts. The content of training in the framework of the module is aimed at the formation of leadership qualities, motivation of professional activity, development of the educational program and adoption of pedagogical decisions. Teacher training is conducted in collaboration with a psychologist and methodologists of the city scientific and methodological center (work in a methodical association, creative groups, mentoring, team building trainings, working at self-education, information and methodological exhibitions).

The "Stalker" module is focused on the administrative and managerial staff of the additional education institution. The content of training within the module is to expand and increase knowledge about the basics of effective team management (management styles, situational management, setting goals, delegation of authority, control, motivation of employees, the role positions of the leader and the subordinate, manipulation in the work of the leader).

The transition of a teacher from one target group to another is continuous and corresponding to the level of professional skill. The main forms and methods of training are: teachers' methodical associations, work in creative groups, social training, coaching, training (team building, stress resistance), mentoring, storytelling, developmental counseling. The integration of non-formal and informal learning provides an opportunity to design a teacher's personal educational sphere without limiting training by the framework of the planned material. In this case, training at each stage (module) is provided in an individual and group form by means of work in creative groups, during trainings, seminars, and meetings of methodical associations.

The gradual realization of the program modules of the corporate training promotes the creation of the personal educational environment and a situation of success for each teacher.

Discussion questions

In order to strengthen the personnel policy in the institution of additional education, purposeful work is done to improve the qualifications of teachers with regard to the modern requirements for people working in the sphere of additional education of children.

The most important factor in organizing corporate training in the additional education institution is a self-developing educational space. The result of continuous personal developing education is a creative individuality, capable to self-development, adapted to technological innovations. In this regard, the problem of finding ways of practical implementation of the theoretical provisions of personal developing education in the field of teacher qualification can only be solved by creating a personal educational sphere of a teacher (an individual route of professional development) and combining formal, non-formal, and informal learning.

The analysis of the results of the control research stage testifies the efficiency of the existing personnel policy in the organization, the presence of the teaching shots with high level of professional competence formation, pedagogical and methodological expertise, modern and productive pedagogical experience, possession of innovative educational technologies.

Conclusion

The system of national education imposes new requirements to the identity of the teacher, highlighting the need of the concept of lifelong and life wide education, which serves as a priority of the modern system of continuous education and professional development of pedagogical shots. The success of the professional activity of the additional education teacher and the formation of the professional position depends on the formation of general and professional competencies.

The practical significance of the implemented program is determined by the ability of the institution to solve the contradiction between the rapid spread of innovations, pedagogical technologies and insufficient possession of them by teachers.

The developed program provides the continuous connection of the system of scientific and methodological work with the educational process in the institution; orientation of the methodological system to the personal educational sphere and the creation of the situation of success for each teacher; increase the professional competence of teachers; creation of conditions for generalization, dissimulation and exchange of pedagogical experience; approbation of innovative forms and methods of training for the purpose of professional development of shots.

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